

**“Comparing the effects of fascial manipulation®
and eccentric training with stretching on
patellar tendinopathy - A
Randomized Clinical Trial”**

Thesis submitted to

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

**in fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the Degree
of**

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

In Physiotherapy

By Research Scholar

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March 2022

CERTIFICATION BY RESEARCH GUIDE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “Comparing the effects of fascial manipulation and eccentric training with stretching on patellar tendinopathy - A Randomized Clinical Trial” by Rajasekar S for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Physiotherapy, is a record of bonafide research work carried out by him under my supervision. The Thesis has reached the standard of the regulations for the degree and it has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, associateship, fellowship or any other similar title to the candidate or any other person (s).

Guide -

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DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I hereby declare that this thesis entitled "Comparing the effects of fascial manipulation® and eccentric training with stretching on patellar tendinopathy - A Randomized Clinical Trial". is a bonafide and genuine research work carried out by me under the guidance of DR. Dinesh K.V.N , Professor in orthopaedics, Srinivas Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Mukka, Mangaluru.

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ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “Comparing the effects of fascial manipulations and eccentric training with stretching on patellar tendinopathy - A Randomized Clinical Trial”. is a bonafide research work done by Rajasekar S. under the guidance of Dr. Dinesh K.V.N Professor, Department Of Orthopedics, Srinivas Medical College Hospital And Research Centre, Mukka, Mangaluru.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction:

Though Eccentric Training (ET) is a commonly prescribed treatment for Patellar Tendinopathy (PT), its lengthy treatment sessions and short term effects are disadvantageous. But, recent systematic reviews suggested that the clinical trials should continue exploring the effectiveness of eccentric training on PT patients as it is more effective comparing other conservative treatments. Decline squat eccentric training and stretching to quadriceps and hamstrings found to be more efficacious than decline squat alone. Fascial Manipulation® (FM) is a unique treatment technique which brings down the excessive muscular tension, thereby facilitating smooth contraction of the muscle, tendon and reduces pain. Preliminary evidence of FM® on PT has been proven effective with single treatment session. However, clinical trials exploring its effectiveness on larger sample size with adequate follow up is lacking. Therefore, this study aimed to compare the effectiveness of commonly prescribed eccentric training against fascial manipulation on patients suffering from PT.

Methods:

It was a randomized clinical trial. 88 patients suffering from PT were included as per inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patients were randomized into decline squat ET and FM® groups. ET group received 5 days of supervised exercise and stretching in a week for 4 weeks and FM® group received 1 session of treatment in a week for 4 weeks. If patients had recovered completely and pain abolished even after the first session, they were not called for further therapy

in FM[®] group. The primary outcome measure was Victorian Institute of Sport Assessment for Patellar Tendinopathy (VISA-P) and secondary outcome measures were 11 point Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), Pressure Pain Threshold (PPT), patellar tendon thickness using color Doppler ultrasonography (US) and 6 point Likert patient satisfaction scale. All outcomes were taken pre-treatment and after 4 weeks of intervention. VISA-P, NPRS and PPT were measured at 3, 6 and 12 months follow ups as well.

Results:

Scores of VISA-P, NPRS and PPT and patellar tendon thickness in both FM[®] group and ET training with stretching group have shown both statistical ($p \leq 0.05$ for all) and clinical significant improvement (95% confidence interval) at 4th week, 3rd months, 6th months and 12th months follow-up. However, the average treatment session for FM[®] group was ranging from 1-2 sessions. 83% of patients perceived complete recovery on likert patient satisfaction scale and the larger effect size index (ESI) for reduction in pain and disability at 4th week were recorded in FM[®] group.

Conclusion:

Though both the groups have shown equal improvement clinically and statistically, FM[®] is superior to ET with stretching in terms of larger effect size, patient satisfaction and less number of treatment sessions.

Key words: Patellar Tendinopathy, Fascial Manipulation[®], Eccentric Training, stretching, VISA –P, decline squat

Introduction

Tendons are passive, collagen-rich tissues appears to be very simple rope-like structure. As structural and biomechanical properties of the tendons are not common, different types of tendons perform various functional roles.¹ Tendinopathy word describes the combination of pain and loss of function originating from tendon.² There are structural changes in tendon as one grows old, but not all age related changes would produce pain and limiting functional activities. However, aging and cumulative loading increase the susceptibility of tendinopathy.³

Hence, to understand the tendon injury, recognizing the tendon structure, its mechanical behavior and repair process after injury are essential. Similar to other soft tissues, tendons are composed of connective cells which include extra cellular matrix (ECM). ECM is comprised of collagen and tenocytes. 60-70% of the tendon collagen tissue is type I collagen that is arranged in a series of hierarchical level. The smallest structural unit is the collagen fibrils. They aggregate into fibers, then fascicles and finally the whole tendon.⁴

The tendon collagens are responsible for high tensile strength and therefore transfer forces produced by the muscle to the bone with less deformation. Tendon also contains elastin, proteoglycans and small amounts of other types of collagens.⁵ Tendons with more positional function stretch through sliding between collagen fibrils and fibers. This sliding is governed by rich proteoglycans which is responsible for more viscoelastic behavior of the tendon.⁶ Whereas, there is less viscous sliding behavior between the fibers and fibrils in energy storing tendons for example patella tendon. Instead, the

sliding occurs predominantly between fascicles and it plays a critical role in energy storing capacity. The fascicles in energy storing tendons are arranged like spring, when the tendon is stretched especially during eccentric loading, the spring can store energy and recoil very effectively. ^{7,8}

Stiffness of the tendons is generally reflected from the linear region of stress strain curve. Positional tendons experience very small amount of loads and stiffer than energy-storing tendons. So, mostly they function within the linear region of the stress strain curve. Energy-storing tendons are more extensible and are often loaded to values close to the absolute failure. Hence, they are at high risk of injuries. ⁷

As far as pathophysiology of the tendon injury is concerned, the process leading to development of tendinopathies is different from sudden tendon rupture. Initially, the reason for tendon pathology was totally attributed to inflammation and then degenerative pathology with minimal inflammatory process was reasoned for tendinopathy.⁹ Various other theoretical models for tendon pathology were proposed by authors in order to assist in clinical decision making.

Continuum model of the tendon pathology was proposed by Cook and Purdam which explains the stages of tendon pathology.^{9,10} It has incorporated clinical, histological and imaging findings of the injured tendon. The early stage was named as reactive tendon pathology which was a response to acute over load or compression. The stage was characterized by non-inflammatory proliferative tissue reaction. The tendon swells up due to up-

regulation of large proteoglycans and an increase in water molecule binding with slightest collagen damage. The second stage was tendon disrepair where there was a greater break down of tissue matrix, collagen separation and proliferation of abnormal tenocytes and slight increase in tendon neovascularity. If suitable healing environment is provided, these two stages are reversible.

The final stage was degenerative tendinopathy which is irreversible for the following pathological findings. There would be extensive disruption of collagen and cell death, ingrowth of nerve and neovessels into the tendon substance. This continuum model of tendon pathology has provided a strong basis for assessment and treatment for tendinopathies especially lower extremity tendinopathies.^{9,10}

The most commonly observed overuse tendinopathies are rotator cuff tendinopathy, medial and lateral epicondylalgia, patellar tendinopathy, gluteal and Achilles tendinopathy. The incidence of lower extremity tendinopathies are higher than osteoarthritis.¹¹

Among lower extremity tendinopathies, patellar tendinopathy (PT) is more common in younger populations, with prevalence rate of 32 to 45% in sports involve jumping like basket ball and volley ball.¹² The incidence of patellar tendinopathy is also high (11.4 per 100 athletes per season)¹³ in young elite level athletes.¹⁴ It has been documented nearly 53% of athletes suffering from PT quit their sports career.¹⁵ PT is also prevalent among people who squat and does stair climbing often¹⁶. Several modifiable risk factors have

been found to be associated with PT.¹⁷ Reduced quadriceps and hamstrings flexibility¹⁸ reduced ankle dorsiflexion range of motion,^{19,20,21} deficit in hip extensors, abductors and external rotators strength^{20,21,22} a stiff landing while jumping²³ are some of the commonly noted risk factors.

Common complaint by PT patients is load-dependent pain especially during eccentric flexion at the inferior pole of the patella.²⁴ As far as conservative treatment for PT is concerned, eccentric exercise has been encouraging, when compared with other conservative treatment strategies such as heavy slow resistance exercise, transverse friction massage, cryotherapy, therapeutic ultrasound and pulsed shock wave therapy.^{25,26} The reason for effectiveness of the eccentric exercise was attributed to progressive tensile load imposed on tendon for its adaptation^{27 28}. However, systematic reviews and meta-analyses on eccentric training for PT has stated that small sample size, short term follow up and home based exercise for 12 weeks were the shortcomings of eccentric exercise program^{29,30,31}.

Although, as mentioned above, various modifiable risk factors are associated with patellar tendinopathy,¹⁷ two year prospective cohort study¹⁸ concluded that only determining factor for the development of PT was muscular flexibility. Among all other physical characteristics including anthropometric variables, and lower extremity alignment, the study found that tightness of quadriceps and hamstrings significantly contribute to the development of PT. Hence, screening for these two muscles tightness and treating them is

warranted in PT. In addition, a cross sectional study found that posterior thigh tightness is associated with morphological PT.³²

A randomized controlled trial combining 4 weeks of supervised decline squat eccentric exercise along with static stretching of quadriceps and hamstrings had yielded better results than decline squat eccentric exercise alone in PT patients³³. The reason for considering decline squat eccentric training over traditional eccentric training on flat foot was that decline squats target the knee extensor mechanism specifically.^{34,35} However, less sample size and 24 weeks follow up were the shortcomings.

Eccentric exercise helps the tendon to adapt its tensile load transmission, thereby, improves load transfer and reduces pain.²⁸ On the other hand, recent studies have shown that fascia plays a significant role in muscle force transmission.^{36,37} Hence, correcting the mechanical properties of the fascia would improve extensibility of the muscles which lead to effective and smooth force transmission to the adjacent connective tissues. This would result in remodelling of the tissues such as tendon, ligament and joint capsule.³⁸

.In case of PT, it has been proposed that improper activation of the quadriceps muscles results in aberrant movement of the knee joint leading to alteration of patellar tendon. , So, the correction of abnormal tension in knee extensors is warranted.³⁹

Fascial Manipulation® (FM) is a manual approach in which therapist assesses patient globally and then apply individualized treatment according to

hypothesis formulated after assessment. The treatment is based on Stecco model which includes body segments, myofascial units, center of coordination (CC) and center of perception (CP).^{40,41} Lack of smooth gliding between inter and intrafascial layers is termed as densification. Therapist identifies the most densified points and then treats them by creating local friction and heat in order to rectify the densification. If the myofascial unit does not glide smoothly, it may produce undue tension and patient perceives pain remote from the densified fascial layer.⁴²

A single group experimental study³⁹ on the effectiveness of FM[®] on patellar tendinopathy was done on eighteen patients. They were manipulated on a densified point in quadriceps muscle for one session. The study results showed that there was a substantial reduction of pain immediately after treatment and the effect was maintained till one month.

Recent cohort study⁴³ has concluded that impairment based multimodal exercise program which includes stretching, joint mobilization, hip and trunk strengthening exercises, single-leg balance exercises, trunk mobility exercises and training to improve landing mechanics may lessen the incidence of PT among young volley ball players. Hence, there is a rationale to identify the densified points of the entire lower extremity myofascial units and treat the patient globally.

FM[®] is a passive manual therapy approach in contrast to eccentric exercise which is more of active intervention. Nevertheless, it would be still logical to compare their treatment efficacy, as both are remodelling the connective

tissue properties and eventually reduce the pain. Moreover, randomized controlled trial exploring the effectiveness of FM[®] on PT against commonly recommended eccentric exercise program is lacking. Therefore, the aim of the study was to compare the effectiveness of FM[®] versus supervised eccentric training and stretching on PT patients. We have hypothesized that FM[®] may be more effective than eccentric training and stretching on PT patients in reducing pain and improving function for long term as it is known for its quick result and global treatment approach.

1.1. Statement of problem:

- Lower extremity tendinopathies are more prevalent than osteoarthritis. Several treatments have been described for PT.
- Though, effectiveness of eccentric exercise on PT has been encouraging against other conservative treatment strategies, small sample size, short term follow up and lengthy home exercise program were the short comings of eccentric training.
- Supervised decline squat eccentric training and static stretching program for 4 weeks was proven to be more effective than decline squat eccentric exercise alone on PT. However, small sample size and intermediate follow up were the shortcomings.
- Single group experimental design investigated the immediate and short term effect of fascial manipulation[®] in 18 patients suffering from PT and only one densified fascial point was treated.
- Though, both eccentric exercise and FM[®] have the ability to change

the mechanical properties of connective tissues and remodel the tendon collagen and reduces the pain, their mid-term and long term effectiveness on reduction of pain and disability in PT and comparing their effectiveness with adequate sample size could not be retrieved.

1.2. Aim of the study:

The aim of the study was to compare the effectiveness of fascial manipulation[®] and supervised decline squat eccentric training with static stretching on patellar tendinopathy.

1.3. Objective of the study

Primary objective:

- a) To know the effectiveness of fascial manipulation [®] on pain and disability using Victorian Institute of Sport Assessment for Patellar Tendinopathy (VISA-P) or VISA-P-Kannada version questionnaire immediately after 4 weeks of treatment period, at 3 months, 6 months and one year follow up in patients suffering from PT.
- b) To know the effectiveness of supervised decline squat eccentric training and static stretching on pain and disability using VISA-P or VISA-P-Kannada version questionnaire immediately after 4 weeks of treatment sessions, at 3 months, 6 months and one year follow up in patients suffering from PT.
- c) To compare the effectiveness of fascial manipulation[®] and supervised

decline squat eccentric training and static stretching on pain and disability using VISA-P or VISA-P-Kannada version questionnaire immediately after 4 weeks of treatment sessions, at 3 months, 6 months and one year follow up in patients suffering from PT

Secondary Objectives:

- d) To know the effectiveness of fascial manipulation[®] on severity of pain using Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) during single leg decline squat, pain pressure threshold (PPT) using algometer immediately after 4 weeks of treatment period, at 3 months, 6 months and one year follow-up in patients suffering from PT.
- e) To know the effectiveness of supervised decline squat eccentric training and static stretching on severity of pain using NPRS during single leg decline squat, PPT using algometer immediately after 4 weeks of treatment sessions, at 3 months, 6 months and one year follow-up in patients suffering from PT.
- f) To compare the effectiveness of fascial manipulation[®] and supervised decline squat eccentric training and static stretching on severity of pain using NPRS during single leg decline squat, PPT using algometer immediately after 4 weeks of treatment sessions, at 3 months, 6 months and one year follow-up in patients suffering from PT.
- g) To know the effectiveness of fascial manipulation[®] immediately after 4 weeks of treatment period on thickness of the tendon hypoechoic area using color Doppler ultrasonography (US) and degree of neo

vascularisation measured by the US and 6 point Likert patient satisfaction scale in patients suffering from PT.

h) To know the effectiveness of supervised eccentric decline squat training and static stretching immediately after 4 weeks of treatment sessions on thickness of the tendon hypoechoic area using color Doppler ultrasonography (US) and degree of neovascularisation measured by the US and 6 point Likert patient satisfaction scale in patients suffering from PT.

i) To compare the effectiveness of fascial manipulation® and supervised decline squat eccentric training and static stretching immediately after 4 weeks of treatment sessions on thickness of the tendon hypoechoic area using color Doppler ultrasonography (US) and degree of neovascularisation measured by the US and 6 point Likert patient satisfaction scale in patients suffering from PT.

1.4. Research hypothesis

Fascial Manipulation® would be more effective than supervised decline squat eccentric training and static stretching for patellar tendinopathy in terms of reducing pain and improving function till one year following treatment.

1.5. Significance of the study:

This study would provide effective treatment strategy that guarantees a quick and long lasting effect on reducing symptoms and improving functions in patients suffering from patellar tendinopathy.

1.6. Operational definition:

1. Fascial manipulation® (FM) is a manual therapy technique in which therapist treats specific area of muscular fascia to bring down the anomalous fascial tension⁴⁰.
2. Eccentric exercise: It is causing lengthening of a skeletal muscle while performing movement towards gravity. The force produced by the muscle is going to be beyond its capability of producing tension as the muscle controlling the movement in a precise manner ⁴⁴
3. Stretching: It has been designed to increase the flexibility of soft tissues by lengthening the adaptively shortened structures⁴⁵.

Review of literature

Study on prevalence of patellar tendinopathy

A cross-sectional study was conducted in 2005 to find the prevalence of jumper's knee among athletes from different sports & to correlate the prevalence to the loading characteristics of the extensor mechanism. Approximately 50 Norwegian male and female athletes at the national elite level were examined from the following 9 sports: athletics, basketball, ice hockey, volleyball, mountaineering, road cycling, soccer, team handball, and wrestling. Examination has comprised an interview on demographic data, a clinical examination, and self-recorded VISA-P questionnaire. Overall PT prevalence was found to be 14.2%, with a significant difference ranging 0%-45% between sports. High prevalence was noted in volleyball (44.6%±6.6%) & basketball (31.9%±6.8%). Prevalence was higher among men (13.5%±3.0%) than women (5.6%±2.2%). Study concluded that prevalence of jumper's knee was high in sports which demands high speed and power for the leg extensors.⁴⁶

Study on VISA-P questionnaire

Quantification of symptoms of patellar tendinopathy would facilitate the research and clinical management of patients suffering from PT. Hence, a group of researchers devised and tested a questionnaire-based method known as the Victorian Institute of Sport Assessment (VISA scale) questionnaire. It assesses symptoms, functional tests and ability to do physical activity in patients suffering from PT. The maximal VISA score is 100 points which is good and the worst score is 0 point. This study found that VISA scale has excellent short-term test-retest, and inter-tester reliability ($r=0.95$) as well as good short-term (one week) stability ($r=0.87$). Mean of the VISA scores were 95 for asymptomatic subjects and 55 in patients suffering from PT. In chronic patellar tendinopathy patients, the score was 22 points in patients before surgery and the VISA scores improved to 49 and 75 at six months and twelve months follow-up respectively after surgery. The results showed the recovery of the patients. Though, the mean scores of VISA has differed between asymptomatic individuals and PT patients, the VISA scale is not a diagnostic tool. Knee pain patients suffering from other than patellar tendinosis, especially patellofemoral pain would not reach high VISA scores. Furthermore, the questionnaire is not appropriate in subjects who are unable to perform functional tests. The study concluded that the VISA score is a reliable index of jumper's knee severity and has the capacity to aid the researchers and clinicians.⁴⁷

Study on Kannada version of VISA-P questionnaire.

This study was aimed to translate the VISA-P questionnaire into Kannada language and performed cross-cultural adaptation of the same following international guidelines. Disability questionnaires are subjective and they have to be duly filled by patients, not to be translated and dictated by clinicians orally to patients' native language. Availability and consistent use of established questionnaires in other languages can facilitate the collection of reliable data. In this study, both patients and asymptomatic subjects, who are native Kannada speaking people, were included in the study. Six steps were followed to translate the VISA questionnaire to Kannada language. To determine reliability, Kannada version of VISA-P (VISA-PK) was given to the subjects twice in one week interval and to validate the VISA-P-K, it was compared against Blazina scale. The test-retest reliability was excellent (ICC 0.97). Internal consistency was good (Cronbach's alpha = 0.98). The VISA-PK showed significant correlation by comparing against Blazina and Spearman's score ($r = 0.72$, $p < 0.01$). The VISA-PK has good psychometric properties and found to be reliable and valid tool. It can be used to quantify symptoms and disability rate among Kannada speaking people suffering from PT.⁴⁸

A 2 year prospective cohort study to determine the intrinsic risk factor associated with development of patellar tendinopathy.

In this cohort study, they included a total of 138 asymptomatic male and female student athletes from physical education department. They were evaluated for various anthropometric variables, leg alignment, muscle strength and tightness. During the period of two year follow-up, 19 out of 138 athletes developed PT. which was confirmed by hypoechoic area in the tendon on ultrasonography. Univariate and stepwise discriminant function analyses found that the muscular flexibility, mainly tightness of quadriceps and hamstrings, was the only factor significantly correlated ($p < 0.05$) with the development of PT. Hence, prevention of PT in athletes should consider the screening of these two muscles flexibility and its treatment.¹⁸

Reliability and validity study on single leg decline squat test

It's a cross-sectional controlled cohort study that was conducted in 2003 to find out the reliability and validity of five squat loading tests for patellar tendinopathy. Those tests were step up, double leg squat, double leg squat on a 25-degree decline board, single leg decline squat on 25 degree decline board, and decline hop .Two groups were included in the study. A total of 56 basketball players, both males and females, were included in the study.

Players suffering from PT who scored less than 90 on VISA questionnaire and control group scored 100 on VISA were included. Each loading test was performed by each subject for baseline & reliability data. SLDS & single leg decline hop detected best change in pain due to intensive training and the study has found that decline tests had better discriminant ability than standard squat test to detect change in symptoms in PT subjects. Therefore, it was concluded that in physical assessment of jumper's knee, single leg decline squat could be recommended & selected best clinical test over decline hop as performance was easy to standardize.⁴⁹

An observational study done for pain assessment in patellar tendinopathy patients using pain pressure threshold.

This study was aimed to make a standardized way of pain assessment in patellar tendinopathy patients and establish a normative values. A total of 234 athletes were included among them 114 diagnosed with PT and 120 healthy controls. Pressure algometer was kept at the inferior pole of the patella and pressed gradually to 50 N in 5 seconds. Based on the ROC analysis, the cut-off point was calculated at 36.8 N. This cut-off point can be used as part of a diagnostic workup; a PPT below 36.8 N can contribute to the likelihood of a diagnosis PT, This optimal cut-off point can be utilised to distinguish between athletes suffering from patellar tendinopathy and healthy athletes. The study concluded that PPT algometry should be considered by clinicians as a pain assessment tool in patients with PT⁵⁰

A study on Fascial Manipulation® for patellar tendinopathy

According to Fascial Manipulation® theory, patellar tendon pain may be due to anomalous fascial tension causing uncoordinated quadriceps contraction.

Therefore, the focus of treatment is not just focusing on patellar tendon itself.

But it should focus on bringing down the tension within the muscular fascia of

the thigh region. This study was done on 18 patients suffering from patellar

tendinopathy treated with fascial manipulation. One densified fascial point

was identified on the thigh and treated for one session. Pain on VAS was

assessed before (67.8) and after treatment (26.5) and follow up was done

after a month. Results showed substantial decrease in pain immediately

after treatment ($p < 0.0001$) and remained unchanged or further improved after

1 month (VAS17.2).³⁹

A systematic review on effectiveness of soft tissue therapy including fascial manipulation in the treatment of knee disorders and knee post-operative conditions:

The term soft tissue therapy (STT) involves passive kneading, pressing and stretching of pathologically tense tissues. This review was aimed to analyse the usefulness of STT in patients suffering from knee pain and knee pain with limited function secondary to knee surgical procedures. Eight articles were included based on inclusion criteria. Out of which six studies were on knee pain and two studies investigated STT effectiveness on post-surgical knee dysfunction. The results have shown that the various techniques of STT has a greater role on facilitating muscle activity, improving flexibility and increasing joint range of motion as well. This study concludes that the STT has very important role in the treatment for orthopaedic patients with various knee joint dysfunctions.⁵¹

A systematic review on effectiveness of Stecco's fascial manipulation® on pain and disability in musculoskeletal pain patients

This review has included all the published randomized and non-randomized controlled trials exploring the effectiveness of fascial manipulation on various musculoskeletal pain conditions. Eight randomized controlled trials, three pre-post designs and two case reports were added for this review as they met inclusion criteria. There were five studies administered only the fascial manipulation, two studies have added exercise along with fascial manipulation and one study substitute the treatment sessions with manual therapy. This review concluded that only low to moderate quality of evidence is available for FM in treating musculoskeletal pain conditions.⁵²

A systematic review of randomized controlled trials on effectiveness of various eccentric exercises program for patellar tendinopathy

A systematic review of randomized controlled trials was done to explore the effectiveness of different eccentric exercise prescription on patellar tendinopathy against other conservative treatment. The included clinical trials had average score of 5.3/10 according to Pedro. Seven studies with total of 165 patients comparing eccentric exercises with no treatment, concentric exercise, alternative concentric exercise protocol, stretching, night splinting and physical agents were considered for the review. The different eccentric exercise programs were decline squat on a 25° decline board or flat foot squat on ground, doing exercise into pain or short of pain. Progression of exercise was made with increasing speed first then loading or only loading. Study results were encouraging for eccentric exercise program, however, poor study quality, with small sample size or short term follow-up periods were the short comings. The review concluded that the eccentric training programme should incorporate a 25° decline board and exercising into the level of discomfort and the athletes should not participate in sports. However, further studies are warranted .²⁹

Tailored exercise program for prevention of patellar tendinopathy

A prospective cross over cohort study explored the effectiveness of tailored exercises programs on the occurrence of patellar tendinopathy (PT) in elite youth jumping athletes. 271 young elite basketball and volleyball player were followed for one year and 270 athletes were followed in the next year. First year, they were just observed and assessed for impairment. The second year, they were treated. The exercises were designed based on the impairment found in the preseason assessment which involved the weight-bearing lunge test, the hamstring bridge test, passive hip internal rotation range of motion and the single-leg squat test. Those tests were chosen as previous study identified them as associated factors with patellar tendinopathy. The risk factors were reduced dorsiflexion range of motion and weakness of the hip muscles . The incidence of PT during the first year period (5.9 per 1,000h of exposure) was significantly on higher side compared to the following intervention year period (2.8 per 1,000h of exposure). Totally, 26 athletes had suffered from PT in the observation year, while only 13 athletes had PT in the intervention year.⁴³

A Randomized controlled trial on eccentric decline squat exercise:

A prospective randomized controlled trials study investigated two types of eccentric exercise programs for the treatment of PT. There were 17 elite volley ball players suffering from PT were included in the study. The patients were divided in to two groups: decline squat eccentric exercise group and step exercise group. The decline group patients performed the squat exercise while standing on a 25° decline board. Patients were encouraged to continue the exercise even if they feel mild pain. The exercises were made more challenging by adding load. On the other hand, the step group patients were performing the single leg squats on a 10 cm step. The exercise should be pain-free and progression was done with speed then load. The total treatment period was 12 weeks. Outcome measures, VISA score of knee function and VAS, were taken before treatment and after 12 weeks of intervention and then 12 months. The study concluded that both the protocols improved pain and function. However, decline squat protocols offer greater clinical gains during rehabilitation program.³⁵

Randomized clinical trial on decline squat eccentric exercise with and without static stretching to quadriceps and hamstrings

A randomized controlled trial was done to compare the effectiveness of supervised eccentric training versus eccentric training with static stretching exercises in PT patients. 22 patients received eccentric training of patellar tendon by performing squatting on 25 degree decline board and static stretching of quadriceps and hamstrings and another group received decline eccentric squat alone for 5 sessions per week in 4 weeks. There were significant differences ($p \leq 0.005$) between VISA-P score at the end of treatment and 6 months follow up. The study had concluded that supervised eccentric training with static stretching was superior to eccentric training alone in reducing pain and improving function in patellar tendinopathy patients at 4th week and 6th month follow-up.³³

Methodology

The study design was a randomized clinical trial and it was approved by the Institutional Doctoral Committee and registered under Srinivas University, Mangalore (registration number SUPHDAHS2018/02). The study synopsis was presented before Institutional Ethical Committee and its approval (Appendix 1) was obtained. The study was registered in Clinical Trials Registry of India (CTRI) and the registration number is CTRI/2019/08/020643. Patients were recruited from August 2019 to October 2020. A total of 146 patients were screened and 88 patients who met inclusion criteria were included in the study. Out of 88 patients, four patients were suffering from bilateral PT.

Inclusion criteria: ^{33,35,53}

- patients aged between 18 and 35 years
- both male and female
- tenderness while palpating on inferior pole of the patella
- positive single leg decline squat test
- VISA-P score should be ≤ 80 , diagnosis was confirmed by the presence of hypoechoic area on ultrasonography

Exclusion criteria:

- if there were clinical signs of acute knee joint inflammation
- presence of other lower extremity injuries,
- local corticosteroid injection in the knee joint with in the last 6 months,
- patellar tendon rupture, and rheumatic disease.

Patients whomever included in the study were suffering from PT for minimum of 7 weeks to more than 3 months.

There were 6 non-athletes and the remaining were either professional or recreational players participating in volley ball, badminton, basketball, weight training in gym.

Study setting:

The patients were recruited from various sports clubs, gyms, Srinivas University volley ball teams and referred patients to physiotherapy musculoskeletal outpatient centre at Institute of physiotherapy, Srinivas University, Mangaluru.

Before assessing for inclusion criteria, patients were given a screening form (Appendix 3) to be filled up. If they had a suspicion of suffering from PT, then, they were assessed for inclusion criteria. All the patients were informed about what the study would involve, and told that they could withdraw at any stage without giving a reason. Once Written informed consent was obtained (Appendix 2) from all the patients, they were randomized into eccentric training (ET) with stretching group and FM[®] group based on block randomization.

The following outcome measures were taken before intervention. Those were VISA-P questionnaire⁴⁷(Appendix 4) or VISA-P-Kannada version⁴⁸(Appendix 5) if a patient was unable to read and understand English, Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) during single leg decline squat test⁵⁴(Appendix 6) Pressure Pain Threshold (PPT) at inferior pole of the patella using pressure

algometer⁵⁰ (Appendix 7) and 6 point Likert patient satisfaction scale⁵⁵ (Appendix 8), Philips ultrasonography affinity 90 scanner™ with a 14 MHz linear array transducer was used to look for the tendon thickness of hypoechoic area and degree of neovascularisation which was measured by a radiologist. The patients were in supine with the knee flexed to 20 degrees and antero-posterior patellar tendon thickness was measured either at 0.5 cm distal from the apex of the patella or 0.5 cm proximal from the tibial tuberosity.⁵⁶

After 4 weeks, all the outcome measures were taken by a blinded outcome assessor. The VISA-P or VISA-P-K, NPRS and PPT during single leg decline squat test were repeated at 3 months, 6 months and 12 months follow up. Flow diagram shows the outline of the study protocol (Figure 6).

Sample size

$Z\alpha=1.96$; $Z\beta$ (80%) =0.84; $\sigma = 19$; $d = 12$

$[d > \text{MDC} = 10.5$; $\text{MDC} = 1.96 \times \text{SEM} \times 2^{1/2}$; $\text{SEM} = \sigma(1 - \text{ICC})^{1/2}$; $\text{ICC} = 0.96$]

$n = 40$ (39.43)

After considering 20% drop-out rate, $n = 44$ (in each group),

Intervention:**Static stretching with single leg eccentric squat training^{33,35}**

For group 1, static stretching was performed to quadriceps and hamstrings muscles and each stretching session was lasted for 30 seconds and repeated for 3 times before starting squatting exercise. There was one minute rest between each stretch. Then, the patients performed three sets of 15 repetitions of unilateral squat on a 25 degrees decline board (figure 1). During every treatment session, squats were performed at a slow speed. While performing squatting, patients counted till 30 .Quadriceps muscle and patellar tendon were loaded eccentrically during standing to squatting. To prevent concentric loading, the opposite leg was used to get back to the starting position. During initial phase of treatment, patients were asked to perform the decline squat without any added weight. Patients continued the exercise even if they had mild pain. If the pain became disabling, they were asked to stop the exercise. Once the squat became pain free, the squat was loaded by adding weights in the back bag (figure 1a). Two minutes rest was provided between each set. There was one treatment session in a day, 5 days in a week and this treatment protocol was continued for four weeks.

Figure 1: Decline squat exercise

Figure 1a: Decline squat exercise - progression

Fascial Manipulation:^{39,40,41}

For group 2, the standardized fascial manipulation[®] assessment protocol was performed first. After the timeline hypothesis was made, movement verification and palpation verification were performed in all three cardinal planes to identify densified and painful centre of coordination (CC) and centre of fusion (CF), in the following body segments; the pes, talus, genu, coccyx and pelvis (figure 2,3,4,5). The most densified and painful CCs and CFs were recorded by using asterisk for each myofascial unit. The data were entered on FM assessment chart (Appendix 9) Then, the patients were treated using elbow or knuckle on each highly densified and most painful CC and CF points

which was marked by 3 asterisks on assessment chart. The treatment lasted for approximately 4 minutes for each point.⁵⁷ After each point treatment, pain was assessed on single leg decline squat test. Patients were called for once in a week for 4 weeks till the densification and pain abolishes and movement becomes pain free. Dosage of treatment varied from single to 4 sessions and it depends on patient's response.

During the treatment period, patients were encouraged to do their routine activity and no exercises were taught to the patients to perform at home for both the groups.

Figure 2: FM® to lateral genu CC point

Figure 3: FM® on medial genu CC point

Figure 4: FM® to Retro lateral genu 1 CF point

Figure 5: FM to Retro medial pes 1 CF point

Figure 6: CONSORT 2010 Flow Diagram

Data Analyses:

Data from the recruited patients were verified for the normal distribution using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. As the data deviated from the normal distribution, descriptive statistics were reported using mean with 95% confidence interval for the demographic and the outcome measures.

Median scores of the outcome measures between the groups were represented using line graphs. Non-parametric inferential statistics, Mann-Whitney U test and Friedman test were used to highlight the difference between and within the groups. Clinical effectiveness was reported using the effect size index (ESI) and 95% confidence interval. The patient satisfaction score was compared between the groups and expressed in percentage.

For all the statistical analyses, the level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$. This would limit Type-I error to less than 5%. Data were analysed using the statistical software, statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 (Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.) for Windows 10.

Results

The demographic dimensions of the recruited samples between the eccentric exercise group and the fascial manipulation[®] group were tabulated in Table 1. There exists no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in the demographic dimensions among them. There were 8 patients drop-outs from both the groups (3 from eccentric training group and 5 from fascial manipulation group). No adverse events were observed during and after the treatment intervention in both the groups. Intention to treat analysis was done and Last Observation Carried Forward (LOCF) method was used for missing data.

Baseline comparison for VISA-P, NPRS, PPT and knee US of patients with PT recruited in eccentric training with stretching and fascial manipulation[®] group were expressed in mean with 95% (CI).^{58,59}

VISA-P, NPRS and PPT, tendon thickness of ultra sound in millimetre and percentage of recruited patients in eccentric exercise and fascial manipulation[®] group with mean (95% confidence interval) were tabulated in Table 2 to 6 respectively.

Median scores of the outcome measures between the groups at baseline, post intervention, follow-up at 3rd, 6th and 1 year were graphically represented using line graphs and that was displayed in Figure 6. Median change scores from baseline of the outcome measures between eccentric exercise group and fascial manipulation[®] group at baseline, post intervention, follow-up at 3rd, 6th and 1 year was displayed in Figure 7. ESI for the outcome measures, VISA-P, NPRS, PPT and patellar tendon thickness measured by US were 1.7, 3.9, 12.8 and 0.8 in eccentric training group respectively. Reduction of tendon

thickness in percentage in eccentric training with stretching group was $8.8\% \pm 7.7\%$ while $16.5\% \pm 13.6\%$ in FM[®] group. ESI for outcome measures VISA-P, NPRS, PPT and tendon thickness in FM[®] group were 5.8, 9.4, 10.1 and 1.6 respectively. The patient satisfaction percentage was 37% completely recovered, 30.7% much better, 19.3% little better and 13% unchanged in eccentric exercise group, while in FM group, 83% completely recovered, 10.7% much better, 6.3% little better (Table 7). The average treatment session for FM was 1.8 sessions (Table 8).

Table 1: Demographic dimensions of patient with knee pain in eccentric exercise and fascial manipulation group.

Demographic dimensions	Eccentric training group	Fascial manipulation group	p-value
Age (years)	21.3 (19.3 to 23.4)	23.1 (20.5 to 25.8)	0.37
Height (cm)	179.6 (174.4 to 182.8)	177.4 (172. to 179.8)	0.36
Weight (kg)	69.2 (62.7 to 67.7)	66.3 (62.4 to 76.3)	0.74
BMI	23.5 (19.5 to 21.5)	22.7 (19.7 to 23.7)	0.54
Years of sports (years)	7.1 (6.2 to 9)	8.5 (7.31 to 1.6)	0.27

Note: Descriptive statistics were expressed in mean (95% confidence interval); * - Mann-Whitney U test.

Table 2: VISA-P of patient with knee pain in eccentric exercise and fascial manipulation group.

VISA-P	Eccentric training group	Fascial manipulation group	Mean difference	p-value
Baseline	60.5 (55.4 to 67.7)	53.1 (46 to 58.3)	7.4 (2.1-15.7)	0.023
Post intervention	84.8 (73.6.2 to 87.9)	93.2 (88.2 to 96.2)	-8.4 (-15.4 to -1.4)	0.031
Baseline-Post intervention	21.3 (11.8 to 30.7)	39.1 (31.6 to 46.5)	-17.3 (-29.3 to -6.27)	0.071
3-month post intervention	88.3 (82.9 to 93.7)	95.9 (92.9 to 98.9)	-7.6 (-13.4 to -1.6)	0.021
Baseline-3-month post intervention	25.8 (17.2 to 36.4)	42.1 (36.8 to 50.6)	-16.3 (-28.2 to -5.7)	0.001
6-month post intervention	96.8 (94.2 to 99.2)	96.1(93.3 to 99.5)	0.7 (-3.5 to 4.1)	0.683
Baseline-6-month post intervention	35.1 (28.9 to 41.3)	44.3 (36.5 to 51.9)	-9.1 (-18.6 to 0.3)	0.047
1 Year post intervention	94.2 (92.0 to 96.8)	95.7(93.6 to 100)	-1.5 (-6.3 to 1.4)	0.018
Baseline-1-Year post intervention	31.4 (26.9 to 38.8)	46.7(37.5 to 51.9)	-15.3 (-20.8 to -2.9)	0.013
P-value	<0.0001	<0.0001		

Note: Descriptive statistics were expressed in mean (95% confidence interval); * - Mann-Whitney U test; ** - Friedman test.

Table 3: NPRS of patient with knee pain in eccentric exercise and fascial manipulation group.

NPRS	Eccentric training group	Fascial manipulation group	Mean difference	p-value
Baseline	7.6 (6.9 to 7.6)	7.8 (6.8 to 7.6)	0.2 (-0.4 to 0.5)	0.88
Post intervention	3.5 (2.5 to 4.2)	1.1 (0.6 to 1.5)	2.3 (1.4 to 3.2)	<0.0001
Baseline-Post intervention	3.7 (3.1 to 4.8)	6.3 (5.6 to 6.6)	-2.6 (-3.2 to -1.2)	<0.0001
3-month post intervention	1.7 (1.5 to 2.3)	0.9 (0.3 to 1.1)	0.8(0.7 to 1.8)	<0.0001
Baseline-3-month post intervention	5.3 (4.9 to 5.8)	6.5 (6.2 to 6.9)	-1.2 (-1.7 to -0.7)	<0.0001
6-month post intervention	0.9 (0.43 to 1.2)	0.6(0.2 to 0.8)	0.3 (-0.1 to 0.8)	0.233
Baseline-6-month post intervention	6.3 (6.2 to 6.8)	6.9 (6.3 to 7.2)	-0.6 (-0.8 to 0.2)	0.35
1 Year post intervention	1.1 (0.8 to 1.3)	0.7 (0.0 to 0.9)	0.4 (0.1 to 1.1)	0.07
Baseline-1-Year post intervention	6.4 (5.8 to 6.6)	6.9 (6.1 to 7.3)	-0.5 (-1.2 to 0.2)	0.063
P-value	<0.0001	<0.0001		

Note: Descriptive statistics were expressed in mean (95% confidence interval); * - Mann-Whitney U test; ** - Friedman test.

Table 4: PPT (N) of patient with knee pain in eccentric exercise and fascial manipulation group.

PPT	Eccentric training group	Fascial manipulation group	Mean difference	p-value
Baseline	30.7 (36.4 to 26.1)	32.7 (36.1 to 24.4)	-2.0 (-10.5 to 9.4)	0.37
Post intervention	53.6 (50.2 to 58.9)	57.3 (53.8 to 64.7)	3.7 (-2.9 to 7.5)	0.098
Baseline-Post intervention	23.4 (17.4 to 31.4)	27.5 (21.6 to 34.5)	4.1(-2.6 to 5.3)	0.16
3-month post intervention	56.1 (52.1 to 62.7)	60.7 (57.7 to 64.6)	4.6(-4.3 to 9.1)	0.35
Baseline-3-month post intervention	23.9 (17.5 to 25.2)	28.5 (21.1 to 32.8)	4.6 (-2.7 to 12.5)	0.285
6-month post intervention	51.5 (50.1 to 59.2)	59.1 (52.3 to 64.5)	7.6 (-9.1 to 3.3)	0.270
Baseline-6-month post intervention	22.3 (16.0 to 31.5)	27.7 (20.6 to 31.7)	5.4 (-9.5 to 15.7)	0.353
1 Year post intervention	51.1 (61.4 to 49.6)	63.7 (58.7 to 67.7)	12.6 (-8.6 to 20.3)	0.426
Baseline-1-Year post intervention	22.3 (17.6 to 30.0)	34.2(28.4 to 41.5)	11.9 (-8.6 to 24.4)	0.468
P-value	<0.0001	<0.0001		

Note: Descriptive statistics were expressed in mean (95% confidence interval); * - Mann-Whitney U test; ** - Friedman test.

Table 5: Knee USG of patient with knee pain in eccentric exercise and fascial manipulation group.

Knee USG	Eccentric training group	Fascial manipulation group	Mean difference	p-value
Baseline	0.4 (0.3 to 0.4)	0.4 (0.4 to 0.5)	-0.04 (-0.1 to 0.02)	0.539
Post intervention	0.3 (0.3 to 0.4)	0.3 (0.3 to 0.4)	-0.01 (-0.1 to 0.1)	0.624
Baseline-Post intervention	0.03 (0.02 to 0.04)	0.08 (0.04 to 0.11)	-0.04 (-0.08 to -0.004)	0.074
P-value	0.001	0.001		

Note: Descriptive statistics were expressed in mean (95% confidence interval); * - Mann-Whitney U test; ** - Friedman test.

Table 6: Reduction of tendon thickness in percentage for eccentric exercise group and fascial manipulation group.

	GROUP	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
US Percentage Change	Eccentric training	44	8.79	7.70	2.24
	Fascial Manipulation	44	16.51	14.66	3.70

Table 7: Likert scores, Frequencies (Percentage)

Likers Score	FM [®] No. Of Patients & %	ET and Stretching No. Of Patients & %
1. Completely recover	36 (81.82%)	17 (38.65)
2. Much better	5 (11.36%)	13 (29.55%)
3. A little better	3 (6.8%)	9 (20.45%)
4. Unchanged		5 (11.36%)
5. Worse		
6. Much worse		

Table 8 : Median, Range and Mean of treatment sessions in fascial manipulation[®] group

No. of Patients	Treatment sessions of fascial manipulation [®]	
21 patients	1 session	Median (IQR) 1 (1,2) Range 1 to 2 Mean 1± 0.8
19 patients	2 session	
2 Patients	3 session	
2 patents	4 session	

Figure 7: Median scores of the outcome measures between eccentric exercise group and fascial manipulation group at baseline, post intervention, follow-ups at 3rd, 6th and 1 year

Discussion

In our study, both decline squat ET with stretching and FM[®] group patients have shown equal improvement on all outcome measures up to 1 year follow up. Due to 12 weeks lengthy home exercise program of decline squat, we have decided to choose 4 weeks of supervised ET, as patients may fail to comply with lengthy home exercise program which may affect the outcome.⁶⁰ On the other hand, FM[®] group patients were treated for a few treatment sessions (maximum of 4 to minimum of 1) in the pace of one session /per week. One week of break is recommended after each session of FM[®] treatment as manipulation creates local inflammation⁶¹. Hence, the range treatment session received by all FM[®] group patients was 1 to 2 sessions.

According to recent systematic review, the average follow up period was 7.7 months by RCTs exploring the effectiveness of FM[®] on musculoskeletal pain conditions and long term follow up studies are warranted.⁵² This study followed up the patients till 12 months. And, though, patients in both the groups improved on all the outcome measures, the effect size was slightly larger in FM[®] group (VISA P 5.8, NPRS 9.4, PPT 10.1 and US 1.6) compared to decline ET group (VISA-P 1.7, NPRS 3.9, PPT 12.8 and US 0.8) at 4th week following intervention except PPT.

Recent systematic reviews and meta-analyses have recommended eccentric exercise for short term benefit and the effectiveness of eccentric exercise should be explored in future studies.^{31,62} In general, reviews on eccentric training have shown positive effect on VISA-P score .The only randomized clinical trial³³ exploring supervised eccentric training along with stretching

showed change in VISA-P score of 42 (CI 33.3 to 48.6) at 4th week and 50 (CI 38.9 to 54.5) at 24th week from baseline values. Whereas in our study, the change of VISA-P score in ET group with static stretching from baseline was 21.3 (CI 11.8 to 30.7) at 4th week, 25.8 (17.2 to 36.4) at 3rd month, 35.1 (28.9 to 41.3) at 6th month and 31.4 (26.9 to 38.8) at 12th month. When compared to our study, the previous study had shown greater VISA-P score improvement from baseline to 4th week and 6th month following eccentric training and stretching. However, the included patients for the group was 22. As, the power analysis was not done and due to less sample size, the result of the study should be interpreted with caution.⁶³

On the other hand, this is the first study, used VISA-P score as an outcome measure following FM[®] in PT patients. The previous single group pre-post study had measured only visual analog scale (VAS) following one session of FM[®]. Though, in this study, the patients improved on VISA P score in FM group in the follow up and the effect size (5.8) was greater at 4 weeks comparing ET with stretching, there was no clinically significant difference between the FM and ET with stretching group at 4th week 8.4 (CI 5.4 to 1.4), 3 months 7.6 (CI 13.4 to 1.6), 6th month 0.7 (CI 3.5 to 4.1) and 12 month 1.5 (CI 6.3 to 1.4) follow-up. The mean difference of improvement between the groups was much lower than minimal clinical important score of 13 for VISA⁶⁴. The confidence interval for the mean difference at all the follow up was ranging from 1.4 to 13.4. Therefore, there was no clinically meaningful significant difference between the groups on VISA –P score.

As far as pain is concerned, we measured NPRS while patients performing decline squat. In the previous clinical trial on eccentric training with stretching,³³ they used VISA-P to measure pain and function. However, there is no direct relationship between severity of pain and disability and therefore pain and functional status have to be measured separately.⁶⁵ So, we used NPRS while performing decline squat similar to another clinical trial on PT which used both VISA-P and maximum tendon pain on visual analogue scale (VAS) while performing sporting activity.⁵⁶

In our study, there was a clinically significant difference in reduction of pain (MCID score for NPRS is 2 point)⁶⁶ from baseline to 4th week 3.7 (CI 3.1 to 4.8), 3rd month 5.3 (CI 4.9 to 5.8), 6th month 6.3 (CI 6.2 to 6.8) and one year 6.4 (CI 5.8 to 6.6) follow-up for ET with stretching group. Similarly, FM[®] group patients also had significant reduction in pain from baseline to 4th week 6.3 (CI 5.6 to 6.6) and the effect was maintained at 3rd month 6.5 (6.2 to 6.9), 6th month 6.9 (6.3 to 7.2) and 12th month 6.9 (6.1 to 7.3) follow-up. The effect size of NPRS for FM[®] group was greater at 4th week (9.4) when comparing eccentric training group (3.9) and there was a clinically significant mean difference between the groups at 4th week 2.3 (CI 1.4 to 3.2). However, confidence interval varies from 1.4 to 3.2. Hence, it could not be ascertained that all the patients in FM group had clinically significant improvement at 4th week compared to ET and stretching group as MCID for NPRS is 2 point.⁶⁶

When the muscular fascia is altered, coordination of motor units of the implicated muscles is lost. Subsequently, joint movements could cause non-

physiological stretch of the receptors within the fascia, resulting in a nociceptive signal. Theory of FM[®] states that, altered centre of coordination (CC) can be considered as the origin of pain and the centre of perception (CP) is the joint as the area where pain is referred.³⁹ In this study, CC points and CF points were palpated to identify the most densified points at foot, ankle, leg, knee, thigh and pelvis and they were treated.

If the patient was suffering from any other pain concurrently, that was also documented and treated based on which occurred first. One of the patients in FM[®] group had suffered from low back pain (LBP) other than PT. But, he had suffered from PT first then later he developed LBP. Surprisingly, after 2 sessions of FM treatment for PT, his LBP symptoms had improved significantly.

The reason for pain reduction and improved function following FM[®] was attributed to restored intrafascial fibres gliding. By applying manual pressure, temperature was raised at selected areas of the fascia, ground substance transformation happens to convert pathological dense fascia into physiological fluid fascia. Another hypothesis for immediate pain reduction may be due to the fact that intrafascial free nerve endings slide more freely within the fascia and they are not activated at lower threshold.^{67,68} Conditioned Pain Modulation (CPM) might be another reason for pain reduction as it facilitates endogenous pain inhibitory mechanism following FM[®].⁶⁹

The fluidity of ground fibres within fascia could allow for correct deposition of new collagen and elastin fibres according to the line of applied force.⁶⁸ Due to

that, fascial connective tissues would be able to adjust tension during muscular contraction and it leads to set appropriate tension in ligaments and tendons.

This is the reason we had advised FM[®] group patients to continue their routine activity and they were not prescribed any exercises at home. Regaining elasticity of the fascia could also explain the satisfactory results maintained over time.

The reason for pain reduction and improved function following eccentric training and stretching was due to gradual loading and adequate rest (24 hours) which helps to optimize its tensile load bearing capacity of the tendon and reversing the tendon pathology by synthesis of collagen.⁷⁰ The loading was added gradually according to the discomfort and pain reported by the patient while performing exercise.⁷¹ Moreover, the decline squat targets more specifically quadriceps muscle and increases loading on patellar tendon than traditional flat foot squat.⁷²

To our best knowledge, this is the first study used pressure pain threshold (PPT) as outcome measure following decline squat eccentric training with stretching and FM[®]. Patients, in both the groups, PPT values have improved above 50 N (Newtons) at 4 weeks after intervention and the bench mark value to differentiate between normal subjects and patients suffering from PT was 36.8 N.⁷³ In our study, the baseline values of PPT were 30.7 N (36.4 to 32.7) for eccentric training group and 32.7 N (36.1 to 24.4) for fascial manipulation group which were below the normal value.

The effect size of PPT was better in ET group (12.8) compared to FM® group (10.1) at 4th week post intervention period. Evidence has stated that there was a weak correlation between cervical PPT and self-reported neck pain in patients suffering from Whiplash Associated Disorder (WAD) and PPT may be a poor marker of peripheral and central sensitivity.⁷⁴ So, in accordance with the previously mentioned study, despite the pain reduction was more in FM group compared to ET group at 4th week, PPT reduction was not as greater as ET group. However, both the groups had shown clinically significant improvement on PPT values and it was maintained at 3rd month, 6th month and 12th month follow-up in both the group.

Patients had also undergone ultrasonographic examination before intervention and after 4 weeks to look for reduction in thickness of hypoechoic area of the tendon and neovascularization. We had used ultrasonography as one of the inclusion criteria for the diagnosis of exclusion. As fat pad syndrome, deep infrapatellar bursitis, synovial plica and patellafemoral pain syndrome are other causes of anterior knee pain,⁷⁵ differentiating those conditions from PT solely from clinical examination is challenging.

.In our study, we found that there was a reduction in thickness of hypoechoic area of the tendon which was present at 0.5 centimetres proximal to tibial tuberosity in majority of the patients and 0.5 centimetres distal to apex of the patella in few patients. The mean reduction of tendon thickness in percentage for FM group was 16.5%±14.5% and ET group was 8.8% ± 7.6%, whereas, in the previous randomized clinical trial,⁵⁶ there was no change in tendon

thickness following 12 weeks of decline squat eccentric exercise. The reason for no reduction in tendon thickness was attributed to continuous decline squat eccentric training twice a day for 12 weeks without rest period which did not allow reorganization of collagen.^{56,70} Conversely, we have given the rest period of 24 hours between each session, 2 consecutive days break in a week and only one set of exercise was performed in a day.

However, in our study population, the mean thickness of pathological patellar tendon before treatment was 4mm which is contradicting the previous findings of 8mm.⁷⁶ The reason for difference in thickness value may be due to different race and ethnicity as this study was done on Indian population. Apart from the thickness changes, only few patients had shown differences in neovascularization such as some had reduction in vascularity and few had increase in vascularity. Fewer remained unchanged. Our study findings are similar to the study done on chronic achillodynia,⁷⁷ neovascularization was present in asymptomatic tendons and absence of neovascularization was observed in symptomatic tendons.⁷⁸

6 point Likert scale has shown that almost 83% of the patients completely recovered at 4th week following intervention in FM[®] group whereas in ET group, 37% patients recovered completely at 4th week. In the previous clinical trial,⁵⁵ comparing the effectiveness of pulsed shock wave therapy versus sham shock wave therapy along with decline squat eccentric exercise, 6 point Likert patient satisfaction scale was used as outcome measure and found that 2 patients recovered completely out of 15 patients after 24 weeks in shock

wave therapy group whereas 2 patients recovered completely out of 25 patients at 12th week and 5 patients recovered completely out of 24 patients at 24th week follow-up in sham shock wave therapy group. Both the groups received 12 weeks of intense decline squat eccentric training, twice daily.

Patients also reported that the condition was unchanged, worse and much worse at 6th week, 12th week and 24th week follow ups in the above mentioned study.⁵⁵ But, the study did not discuss the reason for worse and much worse reported by the patients. The reason for worsening of the symptoms may be due to intense eccentric training for 12 weeks (twice daily) without rest period, as 24 hours of rest period was recommended for adequate remodelling of collagen.⁷⁰ Conversely, in our study, no patients reported unchanged, worse and much worse in both the groups. The reason may be due to adequate rest period of 2 consecutive days per week and patients performed supervised eccentric training one session per day at 24 hours interval along with static stretching. FM[®] treatment was administered for one session in a week.

The patient satisfaction scale is ideally used to measure quality of doctor's care or hospital performance immediately after post intervention.⁷⁹ Therefore, we did not use the scale in the follow ups like the above mentioned clinical trial.⁵⁵

Though the study has fulfilled the shortcomings of the previous clinical trials exploring the effectiveness of eccentric training and fascial manipulation[®] in terms of adequate sample size and long term follow up, still the study has a

limitation. We did not optimize the treatment on the basis of stages of the tendon pathology which may address the more homogenous group of PT pain patients.⁸⁰ Therefore, future study should aim on effectiveness of FM[®] and ET on homogenous group of PT patients based on the stages of tendon pathology and compare the tailored exercises program and fascial manipulation as both the methods involve assessment of the entire kinematic chain and insist global approach.

Conclusion

Both fascial manipulation[®] and eccentric training with stretching group have shown equal improvement in reducing pain and improving function in short, intermediate and long term follow-up.

However, due to less number of treatment sessions, greater percentage of patients' satisfaction and better effect size of treatment efficacy at 4th week, FM[®] appears to be superior to eccentric training and stretching for patellar tendinopathy.

Hence, the study concludes that FM is a better treatment option compared to supervised decline squat ET training and stretching due to quick and long lasting recovery of patients suffering from patellar tendinopathy.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Ethical Clearance Certificate

SRINIVAS INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES AND RESEARCH CENTRE
Srinivasnagar, Mukka, Surathkal, Mangalore — 574146

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

Certificate Reference Number: *EC/0017/18-19*

PhD Thesis Title : **"Comparing the Effects of fascial manipulation and supervised eccentric training and stretching on patellar tendinopathy a randomized clinical trial "**

Principal Researcher/Investigator: **S.Rajasekar** Professor, College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University, Mangalore.

The institutional ethics committee, SIMS &RC, Mukka has evaluated the protocol of the Project entitled **"Comparing the Effects of fascial manipulation and supervised eccentric training and stretching on patellar tendinopathy on patellar tendinopathy a randomized clinical trial "** On behalf of the Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ethics committee (SIMS & RC), we hereby give ethical approval in respect of the undertakings contained in the above mentioned project and research instrument(s). The Researcher may therefore commence with the research, as from the date of this certificate, using the reference number indicated above.

Member Secretary
SIMS & RC

[Signature]
COORD. OF ETHICS
SIMS & RC
MUKKA, SURATHKAL

Date: *15/09/2018*

Please note that the ethics committee must be informed immediately if

- Any material change in the conditions or undertakings mentioned in the document.
- Any material breaches of ethical undertaking or events that impact upon the ethical conduct of the research

The SIMS & RC EC retains the right to withdraw or amend this ethical clearance certificate if

- Any unethical principal or practices are revealed or suspected
- Relevant information has been withheld or misrepresented.

To collect M. S. Rajasekar

Appendix 2

Consent Form

TITLE: Comparing the Effects of Fascial Manipulation® and supervised eccentric training with stretching on patellar tendinopathy – A Randomized Clinical Trial

Investigator: Mr. S. Rajasekar

Purpose of Research:

I Mr./Ms have been informed by Mr. Rajasekar that, this study involves the comparison of the treatment techniques for patellar tendinopathy

BENEFIT OF THE STUDY:

The findings from the study will provide better treatment option for patellar tendinopathy

PROCEDURE:

I understand that the treatment helps to cure patellar tendinopathy. and I'm informed to co-operate with the treatment regime.

REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL:

I have volunteered myself to participate in this study and I have my rights to discontinue from participating the study at any point of time during the study period. I have also understood that the investigator may terminate my participation in the study at any time after he explained the reason for doing so.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that, the data related to my medical condition would be kept confidential and in case the data are used for any journal publication or for teaching purpose, no identity of mine would be used without my permission..

INJURY STATEMENT:

I fully understood that In case I injure myself during my participation in this study, medical treatment would be provided if required. However, no other compensation would be provided.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understood that, I can enquire more about the study at any time to Rajasekar S on 94481 56719. He would be available to clarify my doubts . I would also be informed of any adverse effects or any other significant new findings during the treatment period. One copy of the consent form would be given to me for further reference.

I have explained Mr./Ms the objective of the clinical trial and the procedure involved in the study and the potential risks and benefits of the study to my level best.

INVESTIGATOR

Screening Questionnaire

Date:

1. Name:
2. Age:
3. Gender:
4. Occupation:
5. Height:
6. Weight:
7. Do you play any sport? If yes then mention.
8. Yes _____ No
9. Which side do you have pain?
Left Right
10. From how many days do you have pain?
7-10 day 10 days to 7 weeks more than 7 weeks
11. Are you diagnosed any rheumatic disease by physician?
Yes No
12. Is there any previous history of knee surgery? If yes, mention
Yes _____ No
13. Have you taken any corticosteroid injection within last 6 months?
Yes No

14. Are you suffering from any other lower extremity problem? If yes then mention

Yes

No

15. If you are currently suffering from knee pain, kindly mention the best matched with your pain location according to the given knee pain map.

If NO, please return the Questionnaire back.

16. When do you experience the knee pain?

Pain during daily activities like stair climbing, sit to stand

Pain at the beginning of sport

Pain only after playing sports

Pain only during sports

Pain at rest

All the above

17. Which activities are causing knee pain?

Squatting (sit to stand) Landing down from a jump

Running

Stair ascending

Stair descending

Folding & unfolding knee after prolonged sitting

Others, please specify

18. Is any treatment taken for the knee pain?

Medication Physiotherapy Surgery

Home-based

No treatment taken

19. How long the treatment was being taken?

Under 1 month

2-3 months

4-5 months

> 6 months

Appendix 4

VISA-P questionnaire

Name: _____ Date: _____

1. For how many minutes can you sit pain free?

0 Minutes 100 Minutes Points

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

2. Do you have pain walking downstairs with a normal gait cycle?

Strong Severe Pain No Pain Points

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

3. Do you have pain at the knee with full active non-weightbearing knee extension?

Strong Severe Pain No Pain Points

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

4. Do you have pain when doing a full weight bearing lunge?

Strong Severe Pain No Pain Points

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

5. Do you have problems squatting?

Unable No Problems Points

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

6. Do you have pain during or immediately after doing 10 single leg hops?

Strong Severe Pain/Unable **No Pain** **Points**

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

7. Are you currently undertaking sport or other physical activity?

- 0 **Not at all**
- 4 **Modified training ± modified competition**
- 7 **Full training ± competition but not at same level as when symptoms began**
- 10 **Competing at the same or higher level as when symptoms began**

8. Please complete **EITHER A, B or C** in this question.

- If you have no pain while undertaking sport please complete **question 8a** only.
- If you have pain while undertaking sport but it does not stop you from completing the activity, please complete **question 8b** only.
- If you have pain that stops you from completing sporting activities, please complete **question 8c** only.

A) If you have no pain while undertaking sport, for how long can you train/practise?

NIL	1-5 min	6-10 min	7-15 min	>15 min	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Points <input type="checkbox"/>				
0	7	14	21	30	

B) If you have some pain while undertaking sport, but it does not stop you from completing your training/practice for how long can you train/practise?

NIL	1-5 min	6-10 min	7-15 min	>15 min	Points
<input type="checkbox"/>					
0	4	10	14	20	

C) If you have pain which stops you from completing your training/practice for how long can you train/practise?

NIL	1-5 min	6-10 min	7-15 min	>15 min	Points
<input type="checkbox"/>					
0	2	5	7	10	

Total VISA Score: _____

Appendix 5

VISA-P Kannada version questionnaire

ವಿಕ್ಷೋರಿಯನ್ ಇನ್ಸ್ಟಿಟ್ಯೂಟ್ ಆಫ್ ಸ್ಟೋರ್ಟ್ ಅಸೆಸ್‌ಮೆಂಟ್ ಮಾಪಕ

ಹೆಸರು: _____
 ವಯಸ್ಸು: _____
 ದಿನಾಂಕ: _____

1. ನೀವು ಎಷ್ಟು ನಿಮಿಷಗಳ ಕಾಲ ನೋವಿಲ್ಲದೆ ಕುಳಿತುಕೊಳ್ಳಬಲ್ಲೀರಿ?
 0 ನಿ. 100 ನಿ.
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

2. ಸಾಧಾರಣವಾಗಿ ಮೆಟ್ಟಿಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಇಳಿಯುವಾಗ ನಿಮಗೆ ನೋವು ಬರುತ್ತದೆಯೇ?
 ತುಂಬಾ ನೋವು ಏನೂ ನೋವಿಲ್ಲ
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

3. ಕಾಲಮೇಲೆ ಶರೀರದ ಭಾಗವನ್ನು ಹಾಕದೇ ಮೋಣಕಾಲನ್ನು ನೆಟ್ಟಗೆ ಮಾಡುವಾಗ ನಿಮಗೆ
 ಮೋಣಕಾಲಲ್ಲಿ ನೋವಿದೆ ಎಂದು ಅನಿಸುತ್ತದೆಯೇ?
 ತುಂಬಾ ನೋವು ಏನೂ ನೋವಿಲ್ಲ
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

4. ಒಂದು ಕಾಲನ್ನು ಮುಂದಕ್ಕೆ ಊರಿ ನಿಂತಾಗ ನಿಮಗೆ ಮೋಣಕಾಲು ನೋಯುತ್ತದೆಯೇ?
 ತುಂಬಾ ನೋವು ಏನೂ ನೋವಿಲ್ಲ
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

5. ಕುಕ್ಕರುಗಾಲಲ್ಲಿ ಕುಳಿತುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ನಿಮಗೆ ತೊಂದರೆಯಿದೆಯೇ
 ಸಾಧ್ಯವಿಲ್ಲ ಏನೂ ಕಷ್ಟವಿಲ್ಲ
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

6. ಹತ್ತು ಬಾರಿ ಒಂದೇ ಕಾಲಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾರ ಹಾಕಿ ಜಿಗಿದ ತಕ್ಷಣ ನಿಮಗೆ ನೋವು ಅನಿಸುತ್ತದೆಯೇ?
 ತುಂಬಾ ನೋವು ಏನೂ ನೋವಿಲ್ಲ
 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

7. ಈಗ ಸದ್ಯ ನೀವು ಯಾವುದೇ ಕ್ರೀಡಾಭ್ಯಾಸ ಅಥವಾ ಯಾವುದೇ ಶಾರೀರಿಕ ವ್ಯಾಯಾಮ
 ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿರುವಿರಾ?
 0 - ಇಲ್ಲವೇ ಇಲ್ಲ

- 4 - ಮಾರ್ಪಡಿಸಿದ ತರಬೇತಿ + ಮಾರ್ಪಡಿಸಿದ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧೆ
 7 - ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ತರಬೇತಿ + ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಾತ್ಮಕ ಆದರೆ ನೋವಿನ ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳು ಬಂದಿರುವ ಮಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಅಲ್ಲ
 10 - ಲಕ್ಷಣಗಳು ಬಂದಿರುವ ಮಟ್ಟಕ್ಕೆ ಅಥವಾ ಅದಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸ್ಪರ್ಧಾತ್ಮಕ

8. ಈ ಕೆಳಗೆ ಬರೆದಿರುವ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವುದಾದರೂ ಒಂದಕ್ಕೆ ಉತ್ತರಿಸಿ.

- ಆಟದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರತರಾಗಿರುವ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿಮಗೆ ನೋವಿಲ್ಲದಿದ್ದರೆ ದಯವಿಟ್ಟು ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ 8.ಆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಪೂರ್ಣಗೊಳಿಸಿ.
- ಆಟದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರತರಾಗಿರುವ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ನಿಮಗೆ ನೋವಿದ್ದು ಆದರೆ ಆ ನೋವು ನಿಮ್ಮ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ನಿಲ್ಲಿಸದಿದ್ದಲ್ಲಿ, ದಯವಿಟ್ಟು ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ 8.ಆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಪೂರ್ಣಗೊಳಿಸಿ.
- ಜಾಸ್ತಿ ನೋವಿನಿಂದ ನೀವು ನಿಮ್ಮ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಲಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲವಾದರೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆ 8.ಇ ಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತರಿಸಿರಿ.

8. ಆ. ಕ್ರೀಡಾಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಿರುವಾಗ ನಿಮಗೆ ನೋವಾದಿದ್ದರೆ ನೀವು ಎಷ್ಟು ಹೊತ್ತು ಕ್ರೀಡಾಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡಬಲ್ಲೀರಿ?

ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ 0-5 ನಿ. 5-10 ನಿ. 11-15ನಿ. 15 ನಿಮಿಷಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಜಾಸ್ತಿ

0 7 14 21 30

ಆ. ಕ್ರೀಡಾಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡುವಾಗ ನಿಮಗೆ ಸ್ವಲ್ಪ ನೋವಾದರೆ ನೀವು ಆ ನೋವನ್ನು ಸಹಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಎಷ್ಟು ಹೊತ್ತು ಕ್ರೀಡಾಭ್ಯಾಸವನ್ನು ಮುಂದುವರಿಸಬಲ್ಲೀರಿ?

ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ 0-5 ನಿ. 5-10 ನಿ. 11-15ನಿ. 15 ನಿಮಿಷಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಜಾಸ್ತಿ

0 7 14 21 30

ಇ. ಕ್ರೀಡಾಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡುವಾಗ ನಿಮಗೆ ಜಾಸ್ತಿ ನೋವಾದರೆ, ನೀವು ಎಷ್ಟು ಹೊತ್ತು ಸಹಿಸಿಕೊಂಡು ಕ್ರೀಡಾಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡಬಲ್ಲೀರಿ?

ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿಲ್ಲ 0-5 ನಿ. 5-10 ನಿ. 11-15ನಿ. 15 ನಿಮಿಷಕ್ಕಿಂತ ಜಾಸ್ತಿ

0 7 14 21 30

ಅಂಕಗಳು: _____

ಒಟ್ಟು ಅಂಕಗಳು: _____

Appendix 6

Single Leg Decline Squat Test

Single Leg Decline Squat Test was done on the following way. Patients were standing on a 25° decline board with arms crossed and trunk vertical. Then they were asked to squat till the knee flexed to 60° and then pain intensity was rated on Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) ranging from 0-10 numerical scale. If knee pain was present, participants were asked to select the area best matching the location from one of 6 areas illustrated on a pain map in the screening form. Three trials with 30s rest between trials were performed and an average pain rating was recorded.

Appendix 7

Pressure pain Threshold of patellar tendon using Pressure Alogmeter

. The PPT measurement was performed while the patient was in supine position with slightly knee joint bending position and the joint was supported by a folded towel for cushioning. In order to access the patellar tendon, the patella was slightly pushed downwards by pressing the proximal pole of the patella. To standardize the procedure, the force was gradually increased to a maximum of 50 N in 5 seconds. If the patient experienced any sense of pain, he/she had to say “stop” and immediately the algometer was removed. The peak force of the measurement was displayed on the algometer. The mean of two measurements was taken for analysis. The second measurement was taken immediately after the first one, with a minimum of 30 seconds between each other, and on the exact same spot.

Appendix 8

6 point Likert scale

Patients were asked to rate about their recovery after 4 weeks of intervention based on the following descriptions from 1 to 6

1: completely recovered

2: much better

3: a little better

4: unchanged

5: worse

6: much worse

Appendix 9

Fascial Manipulation Assessment Chart

Name

Age

Date

Interview

Diagnosis:

	Segm	Loc	Side	History	Rec/Const	Pain modality	ROM	VAS	Notes
Si Pa									
Conc Pa									
Pre Pa									

EXTRIMITY

Caput	Digiti	Pes

Hypothesis

Which plane is involved?

Movement Verification

Frontal plane	Sagittal plane	Horizontal plane

Treatment

Date	CC	Result	Result after 4 weeks